
88. Pinpointing exoplanets

I HAVE ALREADY COVERED several aspects of exoplanet research being enabled by Gaia, amongst them the expected number of astrometric discoveries (essay #19), the importance of star distances in determining the *radii* of transiting planets (essay #21) and, notably, Gaia's first astrometric and photometric discoveries (essay #78).

AT THE END OF JULY, I had the pleasure of attending the 2022 Sagan Summer Workshop, on the campus of the California Institute of Technology, Pasadena. This annual event honours the memory of the late great Carl Sagan. In the context of these troubled times, I thought I'd mention that Sagan was born of a Ukrainian refugee (as was my wife). And, as an example of his prescience, and his oratory, do take a moment to listen to him [testifying to US Congress](#) on the increasingly alarming consequences of climate change... back in 1985!

The topic of this year's workshop was 'exoplanet science in the Gaia era', with some 100 in-person and 800 remote early-stage researchers. The scientific organising committee was chaired by Gaia exoplanet guru Alessandro Sozzetti (Torino) and senior scientist and educator at the American Museum of Natural History (New York), Jackie Faherty. Do take another moment to listen to [Jackie enthusing about Gaia](#) back in 2019!

Contributions from the Gaia side included Anthony Brown's 'Introduction to Gaia', Orlagh Creevey's 'Revolution in stellar astrophysics', and Alessandro Sozzetti's 'Gaia's exoplanet survey', detailing the big expectations for Gaia's astrometric discoveries. Orlagh Creevey (OCA, Nice) leads the coordination unit responsible for the machine-based source parameterisation, and I listened in delight and awe to the resulting statistics (essay #76).

OTHER EXAMPLES of Gaia's contributions to exoplanet science discussed included use in calibrating stellar ages and Galactic kinematics, and ideas for future experiments, including Japan's JASMINE, ESA's Gaia-NIR, and the Roman Space Telescope (formerly WFIRST).

But I will select here just three areas where Gaia is helping to vet, and to pinpoint, these other worlds.

LOCATED ON THE Caltech campus is NExSci, the NASA Exoplanet Science Institute. Of its various tasks, NExSci has developed and maintains several public astronomy data archives and software tools, amongst them the superb [NASA Exoplanet Archive](#), a data service that collates and cross-correlates astronomical data and information on exoplanets and their host stars.

Jessie Christiansen, the Archive's project scientist, gave a fascinating talk which included how Gaia is helping to validate exoplanet candidates being identified by the space transit missions Kepler and TESS.

SOME BACKGROUND. In analysing the enormous amount of data on time-series photometry returned by these transit search missions, it is a huge and challenging task to confirm that a transit *candidate* is truly a transiting planet. Some numbers from NASA's Exoplanet Archive hint at this challenge: as of today, 2711 confirmed planets have been discovered by Kepler, operated between 2009–18. But there remain another 2056 candidates yet to be confirmed (or refuted).

The current statistics from TESS, launched in 2018, are even more dramatic: the archive lists 233 confirmed planets... but with 5808 candidates yet to be confirmed!

Why is it that a regular transit-type signature cannot be taken as unambiguous evidence for a transiting *planet*? As one example, while the fractional brightness changes in a binary-star eclipse are normally much larger, occasionally such an eclipse is grazing, or light from the star is diluted or 'blended' with light from a background or companion eclipsing binary nearby on the plane of the sky. Such 'false-positives' plague both ground and space searches.

In consequence, before upgrading a periodic transit-like signal from a candidate to a confirmed planet, other possibilities must first be excluded. False signals include stellar binaries with grazing eclipses; background eclipsing binaries; background star-planet systems; eclipsing binaries in a hierarchical stellar triple system; eclipsing binaries presenting only secondary eclipses; and a planet orbiting a physical stellar companion.

While the most robust confirmation can be obtained from radial velocity measurements, the majority of the Kepler host stars are faint, making such measurements impractical if not impossible. Accordingly, many clever techniques have been developed to assist confirmation.

The key point underpinning Gaia's role here is that Kepler's pixel size is large: $4 \text{ arcsec} \times 4 \text{ arcsec}$. Within this sky area, binary stars, and even unassociated background stars and eclipsing binaries, can be superposed on the candidate. And if the stellar multiplicity is not understood, inferred planet parameters will be wrong!

Because Gaia identifies stellar binaries down to 0.7 arcsec separation, it can assist with candidate rejection. Gaia quantifies the astrometric 'noise' (the 'RUWE', in Gaia-speak) for each of the 1.46 billion sources with a full astrometric solution in Data Release 3, allowing many false candidates to be swiftly excluded.

The problem is still more acute for TESS, where the pixel size is a hefty $21 \text{ arcsec} \times 21 \text{ arcsec}$, and the assistance of Gaia is proving correspondingly more powerful.

MY SECOND FOCUS is on how Gaia is contributing to clarifying the orbital projection of radial velocity exoplanet candidates. Of more than 5000 exoplanets known today, around 1000 have been discovered by radial velocity measures of the host star. The crucial issue here is that radial velocities are sensitive only to the component of the star's motion *along* the line-of-sight. And it follows that the planet mass can only be estimated to within the uncertainty of $\sin i$, where i is the (unknown) inclination of the orbit to the line-of-sight.

Accordingly, radial velocity discoveries are accompanied by their quoted 'minimum' mass, which may well be planet-like. But the true mass, which can only be provided by Gaia's two-dimensional measurements on the plane of the sky, may be much larger.

Here I will give just two examples of Gaia's contributions from a rapidly expanding literature. The first is HD 92987 b, with a minimum mass of 17 Jupiter masses, and a semi-major axis of 9.6 au, and considered as a promising candidate for direct imaging (Rickman et al., 2019). But the $2087 \pm 19 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ astrometric signal reveals that the orbiting companion is not close to its minimum mass, but instead a $0.25M_{\odot}$ star viewed at a near-polar orbital inclination of 175° (Venner et al., 2021).

My second example is the historically interesting HD 114762 b, with a minimum mass of $11M_{\text{J}}$ (Jupiter masses). It was classified as a 'probable brown dwarf' by Latham et al. (1989), although it has been considered as one of the first possible exoplanet discoveries. Examination of the excess astrometric noise from Gaia vindicates the discoverers' conservative claim, and yields an inclination of about $i = 6^{\circ}$, and hence a companion mass of around $100M_{\text{J}}$, placing it firmly in the brown dwarf (rather than planet) regime (Kiefer 2019).

MY FINAL EXAMPLE, the contribution of Gaia to the discovery of directly 'imaged' exoplanets, is again the subject of a rapidly expanding literature.

Exoplanet imaging represents a considerable technical challenge, both from ground and from space, because of the close (angular) proximity of planets to their host stars, and the very small ratio of the planet-to-stellar brightness. But a number of important objectives nevertheless motivate its pursuit.

These include gaining more direct confirmation of the existence of exoplanets; discovering long-period planets in wide orbits ($a \gtrsim 20 \text{ au}$) that cannot easily be probed by other techniques; identifying and characterising orbital motion; studying formation mechanisms and planet-disk interactions in young protoplanetary disks in which planet formation is ongoing; as a precursor to more extensive spectroscopic investigations; and as a first step towards a far-future goal of resolved spatial imaging of an exoplanet surface.

Today, the number of 'imaged' systems is around 60. Amongst them, Jason Wang's spectacular **time-lapsed movies** illustrate planet orbital motion in β Pictoris, Fomalhaut, 51 Eridanus, and the 4-planet system HR 8799.

WITH ORBIT PERIODS of 20–30 years or more, space astrometry can exploit the near 30-year time interval between the Hipparcos and Gaia proper motions, because each samples the star's reflex motion at very different epochs in a long-period planet orbit.

These 'accelerating systems' can then be used to determine masses for previously imaged planets, or as 'dynamical beacons' to pinpoint where a new planet must lie.

Thus Currie et al. (2020) imaged the companion to the Sun-like star HD 33632 which, at a projected separation of 20 au, induces a 10.5σ Hipparcos–Gaia astrometric acceleration, and gives a dynamical mass of $46 \pm 8M_{\text{J}}$.

Others have also been reported: by Damasso et al. (2020) for π Mens; Franson et al. (2022) who obtained a dynamical mass of $61 \pm 4M_{\text{J}}$ for the companion to HD 984; Kuzuhara et al. (2022) who found a $28M_{\text{J}}$ companion to HIP 21152 in the Hyades cluster; Bonavita et al. (2022) who found 10 companions out of 25 'accelerating' stars; and Kervella et al. (2022) who carried out an even larger statistical survey.

With more imaging observations, and future Gaia releases, many more imaging discoveries lie in the future.

